

Screening rice germplasm against *Fusarium sheath rot* (ShR) disease

S. K. Grewal and M. S. Kang, Plant Pathology Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, Punjab, India

We screened 34 cultivars and lines against the *Fusarium* ShR organism *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld. in the field and in the pot house under artificial inoculation. A spore suspension of the pathogen was sprayed to injured boot leaf sheaths in the pot house and to uninjured boot leaf sheaths in the field.

Disease severity was scored on a 0-4 scale: 0 = no infection; 1 = small brown lesions on boot leaf sheath, some lesions enlarge and coalesce to cover about 25% of the leaf sheath, normal panicle emergence and grain filling; 2 = lesions cover about half the sheath with incomplete panicle exertion, glumes discolored, sterile spikelets; 3 = lesions cover 65% of sheath, panicle struggles to emerge, more than 50% sterile spikelets, severe glume discoloration; and 4 = entire sheath rotted, no panicle emergence, or if panicle emerges, no grain filling.

Cultivars or lines that showed no disease in the field were infected in the

Reaction of rice cultivars or lines to *F. moniliforme*. Ludhiana, India, 1985-86.

Mean disease severity score	Cultivar or lines	
	Field	Pot house
0	1254, 1255, 1259, 1272, 1326, 1336, Bas. 370, Pb. Bas. 1	—
0-1	1168, 1169, 1170, 1173, 1175, 1180, 1195, 1197, 1201, 1202, 1203, 1204, 1205, 1206, 1207, 1208, 1209, 1210, 1213, 1249, 1253, 1254, 1255, 1259, 1272, 1353, PR4141, PR103, IR8	1168, 1169, 1170, 1180, 1195, 1197, 1202, 1203, 1204, 1210, 1213, 1245, 1249, 1253, 1254, 1255, 1259, 1272, 1326, 1336, 1337, 1352, 1353, PR4141, PR103, Bas. 370, Pb. Bas. 1, IR8
1-2	1245, Palman Jaya	579, 1175, 1201, Palman 579
2-3	—	1173, Jaya
3-4	PR106	PR106

pot house (see table). None of the cultivars or lines tested were immune, but disease severity in the pot house was lowest in the lines that showed no infection in the field. Even though most

lines or cultivars were infected, panicle emergence and grain filling were normal. Some high-yielding cultivars (Jaya and PR106) were most susceptible. □

Background resistance to bacterial blight (BB): lesion expansion

C. M. Vera Cruz and T. W. Mew, IRRI

A cultivar's background resistance to BB can be demonstrated indirectly by comparing its relative resistance index to races 1 and 2 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. The index was determined from hill and leaf infection of IR cultivars compared to susceptible check IR24.

We analyzed lesion expansion on infected leaves as an indicator of background resistance. Component measurements may show differences in resistance among IR cultivars possessing the *Xa-4* gene. Six races of the BB pathogen and IR20, IR22, IR26, IR36, IR42, IR48, IR54, IR58, and IR62, all known to carry *Xa-4*, were examined.

Plants were raised in pots in the greenhouse, with two replications/cultivar arranged in a split-split-plot design. Plantings were staggered at 20-d intervals to synchronize inoculation.

Resistance or susceptibility to BB of IR cultivars on the basis of mean lesion area at 15 d after inoculation. Expressed in relation to resistance of susceptible check IR24^a to virulent and avirulent races of *X. c. pv. oryzae*.

Variety	Relative resistance ^b (%)					
	Avirulent race			Virulent race		
	PXO61	PXO112	PXO71	PXO86	PXO79	PXO99
	20 DAS					
IR26	66.3 a	45.2 a	51.1 a	0.4 b	2.6 a	0.0 a
IR22	63.6 ab	34.9 a	7.5 c	0.0 b	-14.2 a	0.5 a
IR20	62.9 ab	40.6 a	18.9 abc	2.3 b	-6.1 a	5.1 a
IR54	61.8 ab	52.7 a	44.5 ab	20.8 ab	7.8 a	1.7 a
IR58	61.2 ab	41.2 a	37.8 abc	3.9 b	-3.4 a	0.0 a
IR48	60.1 ab	40.0 a	40.2 abc	42.8 a	4.7 a	0.7 a
IR36	51.2 ab	40.9 a	10.0 bc	-0.2 b	-8.1 a	0.0 a
IR42	48.9 ab	43.4 a	16.5 abc	23.3 ab	-0.4 a	0.5 a
IR62	27.4 b	39.9 a	25.3 abc	18.0 ab	3.8 a	0.0 a
	40 DAS					
IR54	40.9 a	28.1 a	29.7 ab	12.4 a	2.0 a	26.8 a
IR26	37.8 a	26.1 a	37.4 a	-0.9 ab	-1.6 a	15.3 ab
IR20	36.9 a	23.1 a	23.1 abc	3.8 ab	-2.4 a	12.6 ab
IR58	36.4 a	17.7 a	27.3 abc	7.7 ab	-6.6 a	5.7 bc
IR22	35.2 a	23.5 a	34.4 a	-2.4 b	-0.1 a	15.6 ab
IR48	35.1 a	23.2 a	13.8 bc	10.5 ab	3.6 a	12.5 ab
IR42	34.4 a	27.9 a	13.6 bc	6.5 ab	-4.4 a	6.8 ab
IR36	34.4 a	20.8 a	20.3 abc	-3.6 b	-5.1 a	10.1 bc
IR62	31.8 a	20.9 a	11.5 c	-0.1 ab	-8.4 a	-2.2 c
	60 DAS					
IR54	19.5 a	19.8 a	19.3 a	11.4 a	7.5 a	20.7 a
IR26	19.5 a	19.4 a	18.7 a	0.2 a	-1.2 a	14.9 ab
IR22	19.5 a	20.2 a	13.3 a	-0.6 a	3.1 a	8.4 ab
IR58	18.7 a	19.4 a	14.5 a	-0.4 a	-0.1 a	7.7 b
IR48	17.5 a	15.4 a	12.2 a	6.1 a	7.9 a	11.6 ab
IR36	17.1 a	13.5 a	9.5 a	-2.4 a	-3.3 a	4.3 b
IR62	16.6 a	18.4 a	7.3 a	-0.1 a	-2.4 a	11.6 ab
IR42	16.2 a	16.2 a	9.9 a	-1.3 a	0.9 a	10.3 ab
IR20	13.4 a	15.6 a	16.0 a	4.0 a	4.1 a	8.4 ab

^aEstimated on basis of lesion area. ^b0 = as susceptible as IR24, + = more resistant, - = more susceptible. In a column, treatment means for each DAS having a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.

Resistance of IR varieties to race 1 (PXO86) and race 2 (PXO61) of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Index based on resistance of IR24 0-9 d after inoculation. + = more resistance than IR24, - = more susceptible than IR24.

Three races — PXO86, PXO79, PXO99—virulent on cultivars carrying *Xa-4*, and 3 avirulent races—PXO61, PXO112, and PXO71—were used to inoculate plants at 20, 40, and 60 d after sowing (DAS). IR24, which is not known to carry *Xa-4*, was the susceptible check.

Lesion areas were estimated at 9, 15, and 23 d after inoculation (DAI) and converted to a relative resistance index (RI) based on the lesion area of IR24. (The estimation of RI based on lesion area was similar to that based on hill or leaf infection.) Here, RI is an indication of lesion expansion across time after initial infection.

The IR cultivars showed high relative resistance to the three avirulent races (see table). To the virulent races that matched gene *Xa-4*, relative resistance was low. In all cases, the virulence × resistance index interaction was not significant, apparently indicating that background resistance does not interact with race.

RI for PXO61, avirulent to *Xa-4* and PXO86, virulent, were compared to determine the effect of *Xa-4* and the

corresponding background resistance on selected IR cultivars. By 20 DAS, *Xa-4* had shown its effect, as indicated by high RI to PXO61 (see figure).

Background resistance was indicated by RI unmatched by PXO86. At 40 and 60 DAS, lesions ceased to expand. RI values decreased because of the susceptible check cultivar.

Lesion expansion may be a better parameter to detect the effect of both *Xa-4* and background resistance at an early stage. Such measurements may

provide an accurate assessment of background resistance, as the variance seems to be small. The data also indicate that lesion expansion varies among cultivars.

Our studies also indicate that IR24 may not be the most appropriate susceptible check. If a more susceptible cultivar were used, the difference might be more evident and the background resistance more accurately distinguished. □

Insect resistance

ACM18 (IET7804), a high-yielding gall midge (GM)-resistant rice

S. Sevugaperumal, G. Logiswaran, S. Jebaraj, G. Soundrapandian, and P. C. Sundara Babu, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We evaluated 13 rice cultivars against susceptible and resistant checks for yield potential and reaction to GM in the field. The experiment was in unprotected conditions with 2 replications in 4.8-m² plots. Seedlings

were transplanted at 28 d on 20 Oct 1986, late in the season to capture a high pest population buildup. Susceptible IR20 was planted around the experimental plots to ensure adequate pest pressure.

Damage by GM was estimated as percentage of plants affected and % silvershoots at 50 d after transplanting (DT) and graded according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale. Days to 50% flowering and yield were also recorded.

ACM18 (IET7804), a cross derivative of OR158-5/Rasi, had the lowest GM incidence (2.23%), followed by IET9690, Surekha, and IET9688 (Table 1). ACM18 had the highest grain yield (5.3 t/ha in 120 d), 32.5% more than that of IR20 and 10 d earlier.

Table 1. Reaction to GM and yield of 15 rices. Tamil Nadu, India, 1986.

Culture	50 DT ^a			Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)	% of IR20
	Plants damaged (%)	Silvershoots (%)	Infestation score ^b			
ACM18 (IET7804)	0.33 (0.88)	2.23 (1.37)	3	90	5.3	132.5
IET8629	4.50 (2.23)	11.10 (3.39)	5	75	4.6	115.0
IET8633	1.90 (1.52)	11.56 (3.48)	5	75	3.8	95.0
IET8803	9.60 (3.10)	10.56 (3.32)	5	77	3.6	90.0
IET9234	8.66 (3.01)	10.93 (3.38)	5	100	3.1	77.5
IET9247	2.40 (1.67)	9.03 (3.07)	5	95	2.5	62.5
IET9587	3.50 (1.98)	10.93 (3.36)	5	85	5.1	127.5
IET9688	0.30 (0.87)	4.76 (1.76)	3	99	2.9	72.5
IET9689	1.50 (1.41)	10.30 (3.26)	5	82	4.9	122.5
IET9690	0.60 (0.98)	2.76 (1.46)	3	76	4.6	115.0
IET9692	4.63 (2.26)	10.83 (3.36)	5	89	4.1	102.5
IET9695	3.00 (1.85)	9.16 (3.09)	5	100	1.3	32.5
IET9699	3.30 (1.94)	10.33 (3.24)	5	74	4.4	110.0
Surekha (resistant check)	0.60 (1.02)	4.03 (1.94)	3	90	5.1	127.5
IR20 (susceptible check)	11.86 (3.51)	12.56 (3.62)	5	100	4.0	100.0
LSD (0.05)	(0.65)	(1.15)	—	—	0.9	—

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values. ^b By SES.